

THE EFFECT OF INTEGRATING INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT) IN THE EDUCATIONAL TOOL OF INSTRUCTION OF MANADO INDEPENDENT SCHOOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11634283>

ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the effectiveness of ICT integration in the classroom, exploring various strategies for incorporating ICT procedures into teaching and learning. Technology in education today is largely equated with the use of computers, enabling the storage and playback of diverse media such as textbooks, presentations, images, audio recordings, and videos on computers and mobile devices. Traditional computer education typically focuses on the history, parts, functions, and programming of these machines, often leaving students with skills limited to basic word processing and simple file management. There is a notable gap in emphasizing the use of technology to support teaching and learning. The study involves 96 respondents, comprising 36 teachers and 60 students. The demographic profiles of the respondents include their educational attainment, age, sex, civil status, and number of years in service for teachers and grade level for students. Statistical tools such as percentage, weighted mean, and ranking were used to analyze the data and identify differences in the perceptions of the respondents regarding the effectiveness and improvement of ICT integration. The findings of this study explicitly identify problems, descriptions, perceptions, and recommendations for both teachers and students to improve ICT integration at Manado Independent School. The results reveal a significant difference between teacher and student respondents in the perceived effectiveness of ICT as an educational tool of instruction.

INTRODUCTION

The integration of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) into education is increasingly vital for enhancing teaching and learning processes. ICT encompasses a broad range of technologies, including computers, the internet, multimedia tools, and mobile devices, which are utilized to transmit, process, and store information electronically (Bates, 2015). These technologies provide diverse and immediate responses to educational needs, making them essential for modern pedagogy (Smith, & Anderson, 2018).

Recent studies have highlighted the benefits of ICT in education, such as improved student engagement, enhanced collaborative learning, and the development of critical thinking skills (Higgins et al., 2012). However, despite substantial investments in ICT by Southeast Asian governments, there remains a gap in understanding how teachers effectively integrate these technologies into their teaching practices. This gap underscores the need for empirical research focusing on teachers' perspectives and the factors influencing their ICT adoption.

The rapid technological advancements necessitate ongoing adaptation by educators to ensure the effective use of these tools. Teachers use ICT not only for delivering content but also for monitoring student progress and facilitating communication (Ertmer & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2010). As technology evolves, so too must the methods for integrating it into the classroom to maximize its educational benefits.

This study aims to address the observed gap by exploring the factors that influence teachers' decisions to integrate ICT in teaching and learning. It seeks to provide a model that enhances understanding and offers practical guidance for educators. By focusing on ICT as a mediational tool to engage students in higher-order thinking skills such as analyzing, evaluating, and synthesizing, this study will contribute to the development of effective ICT integration strategies in education (Mishra & Koehler, 2006).

The effective integration of ICT in education holds the potential to transform teaching and learning processes, making them more interactive, collaborative, and student-centered. This study is timely and relevant, as it seeks to bridge the gap in current research and offer practical solutions to optimize the use of ICT in educational settings.

The quality of teaching and learning significantly impacts student outcomes, necessitating the enhancement of teachers' skills and the provision of ICT resources to foster new instructional methods (Olutola, 2015). In Indonesia, teacher education is a critical area of reform. According to the Levin Institute, computers have accelerated the evolution of the global economy, workforce, and education system, fostering international interaction and integration. Teaching and learning resources, such as visual aids, audio aids, and animated pictures, facilitate instruction.

Recent technological advancements have impacted nearly every sector, including education. Enhancing the quality of teaching and learning has become a priority, with governments ensuring that policy documents guide the implementation of significant educational projects. The integration of ICT in education is a crucial aspect of this reform, aimed at improving instructional methods and student engagement. These efforts reflect a global trend towards leveraging technology to create more effective and interactive learning environments.

According to Bonk (2015), ICT integration offers educational opportunities where learners actively engage in acquiring and sharing knowledge, often through social networking and resources like Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs). This approach values learning outside the classroom as much as inside, utilizing a wide range of digital resources. Establishing guidelines for ICT integration is crucial, as they set clear expectations for student knowledge and abilities, providing a framework for national testing, curriculum development, instructional programs, and assessments. These guidelines help teachers plan and deliver effective instruction and make learning objectives clear to students, enhancing their educational experience.

Over the past two decades, the rapid growth of ICT has become a key topic in education due to its potential to create dynamic and proactive learning environments (Ghavifekr, et al, 2014). In the digital era, teachers are encouraged to integrate ICT into their daily teaching, replacing traditional methods with modern tools. This paper focuses on the effectiveness of ICT integration in education, particularly the computer skills and knowledge of primary school teachers, and the extent of ICT use in classrooms. Suat Çapuk (2015) emphasizes that to prepare students for the information society, ICT should be integrated into all levels and subjects of the curriculum. Teachers need to be equipped with skills and knowledge in both ICT and pedagogy to effectively incorporate technology into their teaching, providing opportunities for learners to enjoy and enhance their educational experiences.

Research Questions

This study aimed to find the effect of integrating Information Communication Technology (ICT) in the educational tool of instruction in the Secondary school of Manado Independent School. Specifically, it answers the following questions:

1. What ICT electronic devices promote effective teaching and learning?
2. How often do you use ICT integration in your classroom?
3. How may the benefits of integrating ICT in terms of teaching and learning be described?
4. How may the challenges of using ICT in teaching and learning be described?
5. How can ICT be improved in teaching and learning?

METHODOLOGY

The study focused on the effect of integrating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into the educational tools at Manado Independent School, specifically aiming to determine the effectiveness of ICT integration in the teaching and learning processes of high school students. Conducted from July to September 2019, the research targeted high school students and faculty members. A total of 96 respondents participated, including all 36 high school teachers and 60 randomly selected students from grades 10 to 12. The primary data collection tool was a questionnaire designed to capture the respondents' perspectives on ICT utilization in their educational experiences.

Utilizing a descriptive-causal research design, the study adopted a quantitative approach with a descriptive survey design. This design is appropriate for systematically describing and testing relationships and examining cause-and-effect interactions among variables. The descriptive survey method is particularly suitable for collecting original data from large populations that cannot be observed directly, providing a comprehensive picture of the characteristics under study. Data were organized and analyzed using simple descriptive statistics, including frequency tables, weighted means, percentages, and rankings. The research was conducted at Manado Independent School Parkville Estate, Jl. Walanda Maramis, Kolongan, Manado North Sulawesi, Indonesia, specifically involving high school teachers and students. The findings aimed to offer insights into the current utilization and impact of ICT tools on enhancing the educational experiences at the school.

RESULTS

Respondents of the Study

The study's respondents were Manado Independent School's high school students and teachers. The researchers obtained data directly from 36 high school teachers and 60 selected high school students.

Profile distribution of respondents who were high school instructors and students.

Table 1. Respondents' Distribution

Groups	f	%
Teachers	36	38
Students	60	62
Total	96	100

Table 1 illustrates the distribution of respondents. Thirty-six (36) teachers, or 38%, participated in this study, whereas 60 students, or 62%, were picked from the student population.

Demographic Background of Respondents

The demographic features of high school teacher respondents demonstrated the distribution of groups based on age, gender, duration of teaching experience, civil status, and educational achievement. The following table shows the profiles of the teachers and students who responded.

Profile Distribution of the Teacher Respondents According to their highest educational attainment.

Table 2. Highest Educational Attainment of the Teacher

Degree	f	%	Rank
Doctorate	2	6	3
Masters	20	55	1
Bachelor	14	39	2
Total	36	100	

As shown in table 2, the majority of instructor responses had a master's degree, with a frequency of 20 or 55%, and ranked first. Fourteen (14) or 39% had a bachelor's degree and were rated second, while only two (2) or 6% of the 36 total teacher responders held a doctoral degree and were ranked third.

Profile Distribution of the Teacher Respondents According to Civil Status

Table 3. Civil Status of the Teacher Respondents

Civil Status	f	%	Rank
Married	25	69	1
Single	11	31	2
Total	36	100	

According to table 3, married teachers accounted for 25 or 69% of respondents, followed by single respondents, who accounted for 11 or 31% of the 36 respondents. The majority of respondents were married teachers.

Profile Distribution of the Teacher Respondents according to Gender

Table 4. Gender of the Teacher Respondents

Gender	f	%	Rank
Male	17	47	1
Female	19	53	2
Total	36	100	

As seen in Table 4, the majority of the teacher respondents are female, with 19 or 53%, while male teachers account for 17 or 47% of the total respondents. It appears that female respondents outnumbered male respondents.

Profile Distribution of the Teacher Respondents According to Age

Table 5. Age of the Teacher Respondents

Age	f	%	Rank
25 - 29	10	28	2
30 - 34	20	55	1
35 - 39	4	11	3
40 - 44	2	6	4
Total	36	100	

Table 4 shows the results for the age of the teacher responders who teach in the high school portion of Manado Independent School, which ranges from 20 to 44 years old and up.

According to the data, 20 or 55% of the teachers who responded were between the ages of 30 and 34, ranking first, followed by 10 or 28% who were between the ages of 25 and 29, ranking second. Out of 36 total teacher responders, only 4 (11%) were between the ages of 35 and 39, and only 2 (6%) were between the ages of 40 and 44. The data also shows that the majority of teachers reacted as to age were in the range of 30 to 34 years old.

Profile Distribution of the Teacher Respondents According to Length of Service

Table 6. Length of Service the Teacher Respondents

Length of Service (years)	f	%	Rank
1 – 3	23	64	1
4 – 6	10	28	2
7 – 9	1	3	4
10 and above	2	5	3
Total	36	100	

Table 6 shows the number of years the teacher responses worked in the high school section of Manado Independent School. According to the data, the bulk of teacher respondents' lengths of service varied from one to three years, or 64%, and they placed first. Following that were ten teacher respondents aged four to six years old, with 28%, ranking second. Only 2 or 6% of the instructor respondents were between the ages of 10 and 12, and only 1 or 3% were between the ages of 7 and 9 years old.

Profile distribution of the Student Respondents according to Educational Attainment

Table 7. Grade Level of Student Respondents

Grade	f	%	Rank
10	10	17	3
11	35	58	1
12	15	25	2
Total	60	100	

Table 7 shows the statistical analysis of the grades 10, 11, and 12. The data shows that the majority of the respondents are in grade 11, with a frequency of 35 or 58% and ranked first, followed by grade 12 with 15 or 25% student respondents and ranked second, and grade 10 with a frequency of 10 or 17% out of the 60 total number of student respondents and ranked third.

Profile Distribution of the Student Respondents according to Gender

Table 8. Gender of the Student Respondents

Gender	f	%	Rank
Male	26	43	2
Female	34	57	1
Total	60	100	

Table 8 presents the data as a statistical analysis of the gender of student respondents. This analysis showed that females were the majority of the student respondents with 34 or 57% while the male students were only 26 or 43% out of 60 total number of respondents. It also showed that female responses outweighed male ones.

Profile Distribution of the Student Respondents According to Age

Table 9. Age Summary of the Student Respondents

Age	f	%	Rank
15 -16	45	75	1
17 – 18	13	22	2
19 and above	2	3	3
Total	60	100	

Table 9 shows the statistical analysis of student respondents based on their age. The majority of the students were between the ages of 15 and 16 years old, accounting for 45 or 75% of the total and ranking first. Next in rank was 17 to 18 years of age (22%), with only 2 or 3% of student responses aged 19 and above.

DISCUSSION

A. ICT devices that promote effective teaching and learning in Manado Independent School

Table 10. ICT Devices that Promote Effective Teaching and Learning

Indicators	f	%	Rank
Desktop Computer	72	75	3
Mobile phone	58	60	4
Tablet	30	31	6
Laptop	86	90	2
Scanner	26	27	7
Projector	91	95	1
Smart Board	4	4	8
Printer	46	48	5
Flash Disk Drive	72	75	3

Note: Multiple Responses

Table 10 illustrates the survey results for the most often used and successful devices for ICT integration in the learning process, as reported by teachers and students. The 'Projector' was named the most effective ICT device by 91 respondents (95%). The 'Laptop' came in second, with 86 (90%) respondents believing it useful for teaching and studying. 'Desktop Computer' and 'Flash Disc Memory' tied for third place, with 72 each (75%). The 'Mobile Phone' followed, with 58 respondents (60%) rating it as effective. Next came the 'Printer' (46 respondents, 48%), 'Tablet' (30 respondents, 31%), and 'Scanner' (26 respondents, 27%). The 'Smart Board' was the least-priority device, with only four (4%) respondents calling it effective.

These results show that various ICT devices play a significant role in enhancing the teaching and learning process.

B. How often is the use of ICT integration in the classroom?

Table 11. ICT Integration in the Classroom

Indicators	WM	VI	R
E - book reference	3.80	VO	3
Internet to retrieve information, MS Office PowerPoint, word processing, Spreadsheets, use of email, and flash disks for storage of data.	4.65	A	1
Online learning management system (Schoology, Edmodo, Google Classroom, etc..)	3.81	VO	2
Online social media for communication (Skype, WhatsApp, Messenger, etc..)	2.51	S	4
Average	3.69		

Legend:

Weight	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Symbol
5	4.51 – 5.00	Always	A
4	3.51 – 4.50	Very – Often	VO
3	2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	S
2	1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	R
1	1.00 – 1.50	Never	N

Table 11 provides the weighted mean for ICT integration in the classroom. The instructors and students at Manado Independent School stated that the Internet was the primary method for retrieving information, followed by MS Office PowerPoint, word processing, spreadsheets, email, and flash discs for data storage, with a weighted mean of 4.65 verbally interpreted as 'Always'. The 'Online learning management system like Schoology, Edmodo, Google Classroom' ranked second with a weighted mean of 3.81 and was verbally translated as 'Very Often'. The 'Electronic Book (E-Book)', weighted 3.80 and orally rendered as 'Very Often', came in third place. While 'Online social media for communication like Skype, WhatsApp, Messenger' was ranked fourth with a weighted mean of 2.51 and audibly interpreted.

The results also revealed that teachers usually saw the incorporation of ICT as having a beneficial impact on the delivery of modern education. It boosted teachers' confidence because the use of ICT infused their teaching with vigor and raised pupils' interest and enthusiasm to learn.

C. The Benefits of Integrating ICT in terms of Teaching and Learning Process

Table 12. Benefits of ICT Integration in Teaching and Learning

Indicators	WM	VI	R
Makes learning easier	4.41	A	1
Enhances students' critical thinking	4.18	A	5
Promotes innovation and problem-solving skills of students.	4.23	A	2
Enhances collaborative learning among learners and teachers	4.21	A	3
Promotes research-based teaching and learning.	4.19	A	4
Average	4.24		

Legend:

Weight	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Symbol
5	4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	SA
4	3.51 – 4.50	Agree	A
3	2.51 – 3.50	Moderately Agree	MA
2	1.51 – 2.50	Disagree	D
1	1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree	SD

To assess how teachers and students respond to the benefits of ICT integration, all respondents provide a verbal interpretation of 'Agree'. It demonstrates that teachers and students reaped the most benefits from ICT integration. The variable 'Makes Learning Easier' received the highest rank, with a weighted mean of 4.41. Next was 'Promotes Student Innovation and Problem-Solving Skills', which had a weighted mean of 4.23 and ranked second. 'Enhances Collaborative Learning among Learners and Teachers' came in second with a weighted mean and rank of 4.21. Next in rank was 'Promotes Research-Based Teaching and Learning', with a weighted mean of 4.19, and 'Enhances Students Critical Thinking' was fifth, with a weighted mean of 4.19. Teachers' opinions on the value of ICT integration were also explored.

The majority of teachers stated that they found ICT integration to be more useful because it allowed them to innovate by accessing digital formats and improving their skills using computer applications, as well as the fact that internet research improved their lesson notes and provided them with computer information. In general, most teachers and students provided good feedback and enthusiasm for ICT integration.

D. The challenges of using ICT in teaching and learning

Table 13. Challenges of ICT Integration in Teaching and Learning

Indicators	WM	VI	R
Difficult to keep up with the current trends in education	3.04	MA	2
Time-consuming (<i>ICT teaching requires a lot of time for preparation</i>)	3.59	A	1
Problem-based – learning (Lack of proper information for ICT integration in teaching/learning skills.)	2.72	MA	3
Poor school-administrator support (<i>Limited resources for ICT integration in teaching/learning skills.</i>)	2.31	D	4
Lack of knowledge on how to integrate ICT into teaching.	1.69	D	5
Average	2.67		

Legend:

Weight	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Symbol
5	4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	SA
4	3.51 – 4.50	Agree	A
3	2.51 – 3.50	Moderately Agree	MA
2	1.51 – 2.50	Disagree	D
1	1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree	SD

As indicated in Table 13, ICT instruction takes a significant amount of time to prepare. The respondents scored 'Time Consuming' first, with a weighted mean of 3.59 and a verbal interpretation of 'Agree'. The weighted mean for 'Difficult to keep up with the current developments in schooling' was 3.04, which was orally interpreted as 'Moderately Agree'. The next category was 'Problem-based - learning', which had a weighted mean of 2.72 and was verbally interpreted as 'Moderately Agree'. 'Poor school-administrator support' was ranked fourth with a weighted mean of 2.31 and orally translated as 'Disagree,' while 'Lack of understanding on how to integrate ICT into teaching' was ranked fifth with a weighted mean of 1.69 and verbally interpreted as 'Disagree'.

E. ICT Integration that Can Improve Teaching and Learning

Table 14. ICT Integration to Improve Teaching and Learning

Indicators	WM	VI	R
Integrate ICTs in the learning process, as a key competence and contributing to the acquisition of the target foreign language.	4.68	SA	1
Use ICTs in the classroom to work on information processing, authentic communication, and learner autonomy, as the builder of his or her learning process.	3.90	A	2
Give ICTs a role to help young people be able to arrange, evaluate, and decide on the information that comes to them.	3.76	A	3
Challenge students with different types of supports and formats and, therefore, a great variety of activities in which they pass from receivers to makers.	3.50	MA	4
Average	3.95		

Legend:

Weight	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Symbol
5	4.51 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	SA
4	3.51 – 4.50	Agree	A
3	2.51 – 3.50	Moderately Agree	MA
2	1.51 – 2.50	Disagree	D
1	1.00 – 1.50	Strongly Disagree	SD

Table 13 shows how teachers and students assess the potential for improved teaching and learning when ICT is integrated. The variable 'ICT integration in the teaching and learning process, as a key ability and contributing to the acquisition of the target foreign language' was ranked first, with a verbal interpretation of 'Strongly Agree' and a weighted average of 4.6. Next came 'The use of ICT in the classroom to focus on information processing, authentic communication, and learner autonomy, as the builder of his or her learning process', which had a weighted mean of 3.90 and was verbally interpreted as 'Agree'. 'ICT has a role to help young people be able to arrange, assess, and decide on the information that comes to them' ranked third, with an overall weighted mean of 3.76 and translated as 'Agree'. While 'The problem of students with varied types of assistance and formats' was ranked fourth with a weighted mean of 3.5 and verbally defined as 'Moderately Agree'.

According to the respondents' feedback, ICT integration resulted in an important growth for both teachers and students.

Conclusions

Based on the findings which study yielded the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The statistics presented, as well as the replies of the respondents, demonstrated that the majority of teachers at Manado Independent School used ICT in the classroom. The incorporation of ICT in the classroom had a significant impact on teachers' and students' adoption of the teaching and learning processes. Furthermore, it increased self-motivation to enhance their talents and perform better in all classroom-related duties.
 2. Despite the hurdles connected with ICT integration at Manado Independent School, teachers and students have indicated a willingness to become more acquainted with ICT to stay current with educational trends. Furthermore, teachers and students use a variety of ICT tools for teaching and learning.
 3. Teachers and students observed that the incorporation of ICT to enhance teaching and learning in the classroom was superior to the traditional approach to teaching and learning.
 4. Technology plays an important role in making education more inclusive since it has the potential to increase student academic achievement. However, respondents reported that the curricula used lacked ICT integration.
 5. Access to information through ICT integration helped to minimize communication barriers, particularly during the teaching and learning process. Teachers and students were confronted with several forms of assistance, such as having limited resources for ICT integration in teaching/learning skills, and for teachers, how to properly implement ICT into teaching.
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Recommendations

Given the above findings and conclusions, hereunder are the recommendations:

1. Teachers and students can be proactive in implementing ICT as an effective teaching and learning aid in the classroom.
2. Teachers and students may be exposed to ICT-related training/seminars that can increase their skills in integrating ICT in the classroom and eventually upgrade the implementation by employing virtual e-learning such as Google Class, Edmodo, Schoology, and other e-learning portals.
3. Administrators and principals of the school may examine the critical needs of the academic community, particularly students and teachers, for the availability of computer peripherals in the classroom to supplement, enhance, and sustain their computer abilities.
4. The management can meet the demands of the learners by providing them with updated IT-based curricula that can identify the students' learning demands, such as the rigorous use of internet websites and any other ICT learning enhancements that can promote critical thinking skills and collaborative learning practice among students and teachers.
5. There were numerous ways of teaching called education that might be applied. This paper provided an assessment to demonstrate that through ICT integration, teachers and students will easily be inspired to learn and create better learning environments if school administrators fully support the provision of adequate ICT

resources that may help the teachers and students meet their needs as preparation for noteworthy future tasks.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest in the publication of this research. They maintained the highest ethical standards throughout the study. All respondents gave informed consent and understood they could withdraw at any moment without penalty. The respondents' identities were kept anonymous, and their safety was guaranteed throughout the research process. The study was carried out without any conflicts of interest. Plagiarism was completely prohibited, ensuring the research's originality and integrity. The data were assessed objectively, and the findings were only used for research reasons.

Acknowledgments

The researchers express their deepest appreciation to everyone who contributed to this research. Special thanks to Manado Independent School for the opportunity to conduct the study, Mr. Billy Komulontang, MBA, the School Director, Dr. Vijaya Kollabathula, the High School Principal, and Mr. Imanuel Touwelly, M.Ed., the Vice-Principal for Academic Affairs, for their support and permission to survey teachers and students.

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